

CITY PLANS AND CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGIES IN COLONIAL SRI LANKA

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Abstract: According to the historical sources, the first city plan of Colombo was prepared by an eminent British town planner, Sir Patrick Geddes in 1921. As both a node of the imperial urban structure as well as the political center of Ceylon, Colombo was the pivotal link between the British imperial and the Ceylonese colonial urban systems. Ronald Horvath has noted that the colonial city was the political, military, economic, religious, social and intellectual entry point between the colonizers and the colonized. A majority of the existing research is characterized by its critical special analysis of buildings and city planning including elite and non-elite residential architecture designs in colonial period. But, the subject of extent colonial city planing with the object of projecting of the political power has not been adequately researched. Therefore, this research identifies how the planning, designing and architecture of Colombo city display colonial dominance. In particular, it is presented from a comparative perspective along with similar cities such as Bombay in the contemporary period. This research raises the problem of how colonialists' laid out the symbols of power within the city plan of Colombo. It argues that they paid more attention to massive architectural structures which highlight the political power rather than public utility. The research examines certain specific structures and locations of Colombo (fort, port, military and police quarters, town hall, bungalows etc) within the city plan. In addition try to investigate about perspectives of building construction techniques and methods, power imaged architectural designs, projecting systems. This research hopes to follow the scientific method of identification and the analysis of historical sources such as city plan, administration reports, sessional papers, dispatches, journals, newspapers etc.

Keywords: Colonialism; Building Construction; Construction Technology; City plan.

1. Introduction

There is a new international research interest in the development of port cities all over the world as new trends. This research development of Colombo as a capital port under colonialism is more relevant to opening a new discourse through this current project. Especially, due to the intervention of regional powers such as China and India focusing on the port city in contemporary of Sri Lanka. We must understand the importance of this research in a geopolitical context but focus on the significance of Colombo city from a historical perspective.

The importance of this research no sufficient significant research has been done from the perspective of colonial urban development. This is a pioneering research on colonial urban planning focusing on an in-depth analysis of colonial building construction technology of British colonial Ceylon. The current research by Dharmasiri focuses mainly on the Port.

This research will contribute to knowledge on the development of the city of colonial dominance and the development of the plantation economy for the European market on the metropolitan market.

2.0 Origin of the Colombo City

The Portuguese takeover of Colombo in the early sixteenth century allowed the island they called Ceilao (Ceylon in English) and its inhabitants to start a large exchange and dialogue with southwestern Europe. In doing so, they drew the Island and its peoples into what turned out to be long-term processes of European colonialism and expansion.

The Portuguese, who migrated to Galle in 1505, sailed to Colombo and they are started their construction work in Colombo. According to historical sources reveals that the Portuguese after getting the permission of the King of Kotte, constructed a building with a cabook fortification for their security purpose.

The first to adopt Colombo as their administrative center, the Portuguese built forts, stores, barracks, churches, and residential quarters. The Dutch then used the city as their operational center and expanded their borders. The British made Colombo the capital of their new colony and positioned her as a blossoming metropolis of the east.

2.1 City Plans in Colonial Sri Lanka

The city is a complicated special physical entity created by a variety of social, economic, security, and technological forces. When it comes to the interpretation of the emergence of the cities the following statement by Gideon Sjoberg is more relevant to prove my argument as; the cities emerged focusing on a favorable ecological base, advanced technology, in both the agricultural and non-agricultural spheres, a complex social organization and above all, a well-developed power structure. (Sjoberg 1960:27) This definition can be applied to the Colombo city planning in the 19th century. Many researchers tend to show the Colombo city plane mainly from an economic and cultural perspective. They argue that colonial rulers intended to create Colombo City as a key metropolitan center. During the 19th century under British colonialism, Ceylon rapidly underwent economic change. This research tries to understand and analyze how far the British rulers were interested and attracted to Colombo City. Colombo became important strategically for the safety of the British interest of the bay of Bengol. (Balasingham 1968 : 115) They had a power-proofing agenda and constitutional difficulties also emerged between Governor Ward and the legislative council relating to the cost of military expenses because ward tried to take responsibility for providing military quarters to prepare their residential facilities and the construction of all military work. In 1855, such costs of maintenance amounted to 64.695, inclusive of the permanent military expenditure of 24,000 annually. However, after more serious debate the military charges had increased considerably due to Ward's encouragement and interference.

The important fact is we can understand the real situation of the colonial regime and the extent of their concern in maintaining their military force. The British, therefore, found themselves, in a military defense, strategically secure. The only alteration they made in the fortifications, and to provide a counterguard, on the land approach from the gale face esplanade. Brohier stated that they did this estimating that the hump on the land between the lake and sea was sufficiently elevated for the guns of an approaching enemy to command the work within the fortress. As a security measure, over time, they also replaced the out-of-date cannon on the bastions with a new ordinance. Within this walled segment of Colombo there came to be shown the seeds of British colonialism in a military sense. In its social form, this proved in the long run of the two earlier European powers. (Brohier 2007: 44)

Figure 1: Map of the Colombo Port

2.2 British objects of political power

The British tried to maintain and secure the peace and harmony of these colonies, especially after the 1838 revolt. According to Ward's administration mechanism, he was concerned about and gave priority to the security in Colombo due to the outbreak of the Mutiny in India. Not only in Ceylon, in all colonies taken by conquests, land and buildings that were occupied as military posts and known as military reserves continued to depend on the military authorities until given up with the sanction of the secretary of the war.

(Balasingham 1968 :112) Another important matter was how Governor Ward suggested the maintenance of the fortification in Colombo on the land side and the setting up of two batteries with heavy guns to face attacks from the sea. It is apparent from the policies of Governor Ward that he tried to complete the fortification as a power element. (Balasingham 1968 : 112)

Ifran Habib explains that every colonial power had to develop a colonial urban system that was hierarchically, different from the metropolitan capital and the port cities. He says that the colonial capital and district centers on outlying stations of the colonial bureaucracy and system of military control (Karmakar 2007: 7) The Colombo Fort is comprised of the residences of military and administrative officers, soldiers, and police officers enclosed by Fort walls. John Capper writes that "In those days were not many European residents outside the Fort. The majority of them lived by far dwelt within the city walls. High military officials resided in those times within the walls." (Brohier 2007: 40)

British colonialism endeavored to design the city plan of Colombo in order to ensure their security. The native inhabitants of the city of Colombo living outside the fortress were left undisturbed by the new settlement pattern set up by the British. Brohier says that being imbued by the primitive instinct of herding together for mutual protection, the people had sorted themselves out into communal groups and established themselves in settlements on the tongues of highland by the margin by the sea. (Brohier 2007: 45) This does not explain the British settlers' tendency of living to gather. It was the colonial rulers' sense of insecurity that determined exclusive European settlement in urban centers.

British rulers were determined to create exclusive areas for the residence of their officers. Accordingly, they removed slums of

low-income city dwellers from areas surrounding the fort. Due to this they tried to develop the Cinnamon Garden area for the European elite. They tried to keep their location without any kind of disturbance from the low-income people due to security reasons. According to Prof Geddis, this urban planning scheme reveals their primary concern; 'This is not a cause for satisfaction by any means. If history were a guide, one may even say that revolutionary upheaval is engendered only in such conditions...' (Hullugalle 1965: 174) In this current research, it is able to clarify us that though the Colonialists tried to show that their vision was genuine and transparent, but actual practice was different and they had objectives entrenched in political power. However, many historians tried to show that the British rulers built gardens and parks such as Victoria Park for the benefit of the common people. This research reveals that the British colonial attitude towards the civilians is different.

The current research shows that the British rulers focused their attention on the micro setup of the city plan and maintained it without any disturbance to suit their own power agenda. If they expected some kind of security issues, they changed it. This research was able to prove this idea through the classic example maintain which the Slave Island's location. The British rulers paid their attention to the Slave Island considering that it was a tongue of land joined to the Fort by bridge and causeways. 'Slave Island' was so called because slaves were segregated there by the Dutch and the British rulers also identified this place as the most essential security place for their own agenda and converted slave island into the home of a company of the Malay regiment. This place prepared them and included an excellent parade ground regiment also. This applies to Colombo from the time of the Dutch who kept out the native population from the fort of Colombo.

Dipesh Karmarkar also pointed out that the major task of the Bombay port project under the British colonial period depended on basing, building and organizing Bombay's space to serve their colonial imperial agenda. (Karmarkar 2007: 4)

When we compare the condition of the Bombay city plan it reveals that the British rulers when building the new dock at Mazgaon the dwellings of poor people between the church gate and Bazar gate were demolished. In 1772 an order was issued reserving the areas south of the church street for Europeans that compelled the natives to take quarters north of the Bazar street outside the town hall. (Karmarkar 2007:7) This research further reveals that the aspects of the colonial agenda behind city planning are similar in the Asian region.

2.3 Residential Structures.

This research attempts to portray the picture of the structures and designs. Hullugalla portrays the real picture of the city plan of Colombo under the British colonial period. He says that Governor Sir Henry Ward had a promenade that skirts the seafront built which was completed in 1859. As the description has it, he "recommended it to his successors in the interest of the Ladies and children of Colombo" (Hullugalle 1965: 34) Furthermore, he stated that, on the opposite side of the esplanade there was the Race Course until this was moved to Cinnamon Gardens. The southern end of the esplanade led to Kollupitiya, a flourishing suburb. On each side of the road stood a number of beautiful Villas shaded by lovely gardens. (Hullugalle 1965: 34)

Another important residential place Cinnamon gardens, too became a fashionable suburb with palatial houses, though with cinnamon plantations around, there was more of a rural atmosphere. When we focus our attention on

the Banglows of Cinnamon Gardens, more influential Europeans lived in this location under the colonial regime. Grand pass, Mutwal and Wolvendaal in Colombo north characterized other important residential places in Colombo city having palatial type residential dwellings and a greener environmental atmosphere. Gavin Hamilton - The collector of customs, Sir William Coke-the Chief Justice and the Auditor general and other prestigious officers lived in this location in Mutwall. (Hullugalle 1965: 32-34) The Rev. James Cordiner gives us an important description of Colombo at the beginning of the nineteenth century. He says that "The Pettah is neat, clean, regular and larger than within the Fort. Five streets, each half a mile in length, run parallel to and another: and the same number interest them at right angles." Varandhas supported of lofty pillars which shade the fronts of the houses, but they want the additional ornaments of trees" (Hullugalle 1965:33)

Figure 2 : Colombo Fort Presidential Secretariat Building in Sri Lanka - build in 1930

2.4 Construction method and technology

This research focus on the housing construction methods of the British colonial period and it reveals that a common solution to the lack of affordable dwellings was the construction of single storied, mostly detached, small housing units using less durable material. Building their own houses with materials available in the new environment and using self-help methods to do so, represent

the transfer of rural housing methods to the city. These buildings helped the inhabitants to familiarize themselves with the city, and, at the same time, also a rural part of it.

When we investigate the houses, they were generally built of cabook, with thick walls neatly washed with chunnam, and lofty roof. (Brohier 2007: 60) High roofs were used for greater ventilation. Hence it was noted that while the ram parted fort was hot, Pettah was cool looking from ground level. A person, who is walking through the straight streets which composed the grid, can see parallel rows of slender wooden or rounded brick pillars on both sides of the roads, which seemed to converge in the distance. These pillar fronted verandahs and were separated from the street, which was a few feet below them only a wooden railing. (Brohier 2007: 30)

This research tries to trace the real situation of the construction method of the colonial period focusing on the main street in Colombo. When we portray the real picture of the fruit and vegetable market at the end of main street Pettah.

The Beira lake, which was much larger than it is today The Beira lake, which was much larger than it is today, afforded the favorite and healthy recreation of boating in all its phases. It was put to much use as the arena for this truly English aquatic amusement. Small sailing vessels and row boats, pleasure barges and skiffs increased in consequence. The only adverse note added to the enjoyment was that the sport was spoilt to some extent by the "inordinate growth of water , afforded the favorite and healthy recreation of boating in all its phases. It was put to much use as the arena for this truly English aquatic amusement. Small sailing vessels and row boats, pleasure barges and skiffs increased in consequence. The only adverse note added to the enjoyment was that

the sport was spoilt to some extent by the "inordinate growth of water weeds". It is interesting to recall that regattas were frequently organized in those times. In such occasions the Lake put on a most gay and animated appearance with nearly all the crafts dressed in bunting, and at night illuminated using coloured lanterns. Such are the picturesque vistas the Beira Lake offered when it was an ornament of the city. Furthermore, it is revealed that many people lived in "Villas" built in the middle of the nineteenth century, which illustrates the typical make-shift structures that existed in the Pettah. (Brohier 2007: 46) They even used a small number of tile roofed buildings supported on columns of brick or wood. According to the official census reports of 1814 the number of tiled houses within graves (the fort, pettah and the four gravets) was limited to 2654 and during the census of 1825 it had increased to only 3801. This information reveals that this tile using trend expanded gradually in this period. Another significant fact was that though applying floor tiles is a popular culture in the modern society, this practice could be also seen in this particular period. (Brohier 2007: 85)

2.5 Construction method of harbor

In 1864, another major construction project was the public scheme to convert the Galle Face cemetery and the barracks into a dock for ships by a professional harbor engineer named Franklin by, having an entrance from the sea through the Galle Face road. The main argument stated above becomes stronger as the harbor construction mechanism in the colonial period also focused on the security purpose.

According to Dharmasena, the harbor was expanded in 1874 to accommodate fifty steamers and a breakwater was constructed. This condition had a more significant impact on the Colombo landscape. By the 1890s, the docks had become one of the most significant

places in the city. Outside the port, the expanding labor force transformed the north of the Fort (Kochchikade) into one of the first urban working-class settlements. (Dharmasena 1980: 23)

Another important fact is that according to the British colonial agenda they gave priority to military establishment and their military objective also combined with the colonial communication system. Institutions carried out road networks and the interior military outposts, and these institutions carried out road construction. The British stationed troops at Kandy, Trincomalee and the chief towns between Colombo and these; these roads were capable of supporting troop movement, by connecting those locations. In 1832, Royal engineers in charge of road building were under the quartermaster general, the officer who oversaw the military barracks. (Perera 1999: 43)

It is important to draw our attention to understand the construction technology relating to the harbor sector in the British colonial period. The construction work of the south west breakwater in Colombo harbor was overseen by a leading member and master of attendance, captain Legge. A landing jetty was constructed for use in connection with the light house work. The jetty had boat steps and a landing stage and communication with the light house was possible during the monsoon when heavy waves ran over the breakwater generally. (Dharmasena 1980: 53)

The Colombo port rapidly developed the demand of influence of the planters and commercial community resultant of the plantation economy. The obvious demand of these visitors was for accommodation of European standard. By 1900 the Grand Orientals, The Bristol and The Galle Face hotels of all them in the Fort, and all them owned to Europeans. And by the time, former residence of Ceylon's governors has been converted into

the Mount Lavinia Hotel, some seven miles of the city (Ferguson 1878: 75)

Figure 3: Light House - Colombo

If we consider the commercial development, work was begun in 1817 and by 1922 three oil companies established its storage tanks for petrol, fuel oil and kerosene at Kolonnawa. The Asiatic petroleum company and the standard oil company of New York had both set up buildings and machinery for the manufacture of kerosene cans. To pump liquid a ten inch pipe line adjoining the new railway line from Kolonnawa to the jetties, with a connecting link at Bloemendal was setup. In addition to this, harbor construction work was progress due to the fact heavy demand of merchant community cargo sector rapidly which was developing at Kochchikade.

Major construction was the lake -harbor canal scheme. It was part of the construction of the ware house along the harbor canal as well as the massive Manning markets comprising 58 markets and 19 godowns. The project works consisted of a canal connecting the harbor with the lake, together with the necessary locks, warehouses, basing, bridges etc. (Dharmasena 1980: 96)

Another important fact was by the early 20s, the fort was connected with the main railway system and the congestion of good vehicles at customs warehouses was avoided, no more breaking bulk was necessary and the cost handling was considerably reduced. Direct

transit between merchant stores on the lakeside and the harbor area was secured and roads to that extent were relieved. Lake became geographically and economically a part of the port. According historical sources, it reveals that a charge of only 30 cents of per ton of good was levied for the use of the lake harbor canal. (Administration Report 1922 :38)

Figure 4: Colombo City

As the harbor expanded and the volume of shipping increased the shortage of fort workers created problems for the British. Accordingly a large number of South Indians especially from Cochin were imported and settled in the Kochchikade area as port workers. Even prisoners were used for fort work.

2.6 Town Hall

The British colonial agenda was more concerned about city building desing focusing on creating a dignified position. In 1921 Prof Patrick Gedds, the distinguished town planner, suggested a more spacious side. According to his preliminary report, we can identify that they built these major buildings to demonstrate their colonial prestige as well as to frighten the civilians:

"I can find out in the entire city, and this after going over every other situation .I have heard suggested of the needed ,large ,central and dignified position required for the municipal buildings..."(Hullugalle 1965: 74) The aforementioned argument is strengthened further when we consider idea of the designer of the Town hall in the British period. Mr. A. Woodeson, the Ceylon Government Architect wrote about Mr. Edwards designer of Town

hall as follows: “ The buildings are admirable led out on the side; the out buldings are well secluded, but very accessiable. The main bulding stands out prominently and would commnd pleasing views from all angles. (Hullugalle 1965: 74)

Figure 5 : Town Hall Colombo

3.0 Conclusion.

Colombo, as a city, was developed to accommodate two requirements, firstly the security of British power and the colonial ruling class and secondly to cater to the needs of a colony that has evolved as a profitable Cochchicade area as port workers. Even prisoners were used for fort work. 2.6 Town Hall possession with the rapid expansion of plantation. That made Colombo as a large commercial metropolis.

This research project identifies the construction technologies and the materials were used in the British colonial period in Sri Lanka. The study course, analysis and the surveying reveal that the British’s has used their machines, construction methods and other techniques for their own purposes. They highlight their dignity, prestige and colonial image through the architectural structures. The most important finding is that the British’s has used local materials too for the construction process such as bricks, to emphasise their colonial image in Sri Lanka. Most of the time, British colonials reconstructed huge buildings to show the dominante and hierarchical image. The

objective of the power agenda was more strongly proved through these structures.

This research consists a common micro analysis on the use of objectives of military powers and political powers to emerge through the city plans and construction technology in colonial Sri Lanka. These technologies, methodologies and forms of the constructions such as the light house and town hall have become heritages in modern Sri Lanka. It is important to make a process to creat them as national sources and heritages.

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